

EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17175730>

Abstract. This article analyzes the relevance of educating youth in the spirit of patriotism, problems in this area, and ways to overcome them. In particular, it examines issues such as information attacks, insufficient influence of family and school, and a lack of educational materials in curricula. Additionally, practical proposals are put forward for reforms in the education system, effective use of mass media and Internet resources, and strengthening patriotic education through family upbringing and youth association activities. The article advocates for a comprehensive approach to instilling the idea of patriotism in the minds of the younger generation.

Keywords. Youth, patriotism, national idea, upbringing, education, information attack, internet, mass media, family upbringing, civil society, national values.

"There are many young people among you who set an example for others in terms of patriotism, kindness, and humanity. It is no exaggeration to say that these sons and daughters are the golden fund of our people, the builders of the Third Renaissance. Such dedicated, educated, intelligent, and patriotic sons and daughters, who are considered the future of New Uzbekistan, should be an example for everyone. Taking this opportunity, I would like to express my gratitude to these devoted and patriotic young men and women. We must comprehensively support such noble and charitable projects."

The development of an independent state and its future depends on the younger generation. Therefore, educating young people in the spirit of national ideology, patriotism, humanism, and selflessness is one of the important tasks of any society. This issue is becoming even more relevant in the 21st century, in the era of globalization and information attacks. Patriotism is a person's love for their Homeland, their desire to protect and develop it, and their readiness to actively participate in its progress. It is closely connected with the history, culture, and values of the people and is formed on the basis of generational continuity. The cultivation of patriotism among young people plays an important role in ensuring stability in society, protecting youth from destructive ideas, and raising them as socially active individuals. Appreciation of independence, respect for state symbols, preservation of national unity - all these are the results of a sense of patriotism.

Unfortunately, it is no secret to any of us that nowadays there are many ways and methods of poisoning the minds of young people and leading them away from their intended goals. Here are a few examples:

1. Information attacks and poisoning of the minds of young people

Various alien ideas, information without a clear source, disseminated through the Internet and social networks, can cause indifference to national values among young people.

2. Sufficient influence of family and school

In some cases, insufficient upbringing in the family and educational institutions leads to insufficient formation of a sense of patriotism in young people. In preschool educational institutions and schools, more attention is paid not to practical education, national values, the heroism of our great ancestors, their contribution to the development of the world, but, on the contrary, to theoretical knowledge. This, in turn, leads to the loss of patriotism in young people.

3. Lack of educational materials in the curricula

Issues of patriotism are rarely included in the curricula. This limits the possibility of awakening a sense of patriotism in young people through science.

4. Use of mass media and Internet resources.

1. Reforms in the education system

- Increase the inclusion of materials on the national idea and patriotism in the curriculum;

- Organization of educational activities on a practical basis, not a theoretical one;
- Teachers themselves must be loyal to national ideals.

We want to focus on the use of mass media and internet resources. Today, information is manifested as one of the main factors influencing the consciousness and thinking of society. Especially in the lives of young people, the role of mass media (media) and internet resources is invaluable. Therefore, the effective use of these tools in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is becoming an important part of the process of modern pedagogy and social education.

The information space has a two-sided effect:

- Positive impact: Materials about the national idea, historical heritage, and achievements of compatriots strengthen the sense of pride in young people.
- Negative impact: Foreign ideas, information from unknown sources, and manipulation on social networks poison young people's minds and form vices such as indifference to their nation, history, or state. Therefore, it is very important to increase information literacy among young people and develop critical thinking skills. The inability to achieve these vices by restricting the internet further clouds one's heart.

Effective ways of promoting patriotic ideas

Development of national media projects:

Wide coverage of the lives of national heroes, historical figures, and contemporary compatriots through television programs, documentaries, and interviews.

Creation of sections such as "My Homeland," "Let's Be a Worthy Descendant of Our Ancestors," "Lessons of Heroism," "Youth and the Future," "I Will Certainly Be a Patriot."

Patriotic content on social networks:

Distribution of short, impactful videos, infographics, and motivational speeches through YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, and Telegram channels.

Organization of flash mobs and challenges promoting national ideas with the participation of bloggers and influencers (for example: My Hero, Pride of the Motherland, etc.).

Educational platforms through information technologies:

Creation of online courses on the history of the Motherland, national symbols, state structure, mobile applications (based on gamification).

Conducting interactive events online, such as "Patriotism Quiz," "National Idea Quiz."

Media literacy that fosters critical thinking:

Organization of seminars and webinars among young people on identifying "fake" information, working with reliable sources.

Conducting promotional work on the topic "Immunity against information attacks" through the media.

Creating personal brands of heroes:

Preparation of special projects about domestic scientists, military personnel, inventors, athletes, and entrepreneurs of Uzbekistan.

Showing an example to young people through their lives is an example of patriotism in real life.

In the relevant resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the educational function of the media. For example, the Law "On Youth Policy," adopted in 2021, defines cooperation with the media as one of the important tasks in strengthening patriotic ideas in the minds of young people.

Participation of youth associations and civil society institutions

- structures such as the "Youth Union," volunteer organizations should actively organize patriotic events;

- It is necessary to involve young people in the fate of the Motherland through various projects and activities.

In preparing this scientific article, we relied on a number of regulatory legal acts, scientific sources, and analytical articles published in the mass media on patriotic education, the national idea, and youth policy.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the duty of every citizen to love and defend the Motherland. This fundamental document serves as the legal foundation for fostering patriotism among young people.

The speeches of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev - especially within the framework of the idea of the Third Renaissance, calling young people to selflessness and patriotism - form the ideological basis of the article. In the President's speech, youth is assessed as the "golden fund of our people."

N. Ahmedova, J. Rakhmatov. "Fundamentals of National Idea and Spirituality" (2020) - this textbook extensively covers the content of the national idea, its role in education, and its influence on the consciousness of young people. The ideological views in the article were inspired by this very source.

I.A. Karimov. "High Spirituality - Invincible Force" (2008) - the strategic importance of spiritual education for the state and society is highlighted in detail. In the author's opinion, development is impossible without spiritual perfection.

B. Mamarasulov. In the article "Patriotism Education: Theoretical and Practical Foundations" (2023), real problems among young people are analyzed and solutions based on pedagogical approaches are proposed. This article is rich in analyses related to the state of today's young generation in the information environment.

Based on the analysis of the literature, it can be said that education in the spirit of patriotism has a solid scientific and legal basis both theoretically and practically. Among the sources used, the speeches of the head of state, scientific literature, and current laws complement each other, increasing the vitality and reliability of the article. This indicates the

need for more comprehensive and targeted work to strengthen patriotic ideas in the minds of young people.

In the context of modern globalization and information attacks, educating the younger generation in the spirit of the national idea and patriotism is of decisive importance for the stability of society, the spiritual foundation of the nation, and the future of the state. In this article, the essence of the concept of patriotism, its historical and spiritual foundations, the influence of mass media and internet resources on the formation of this feeling in the minds of the younger generation, and ways of their effective use are analyzed in detail.

Based on the analysis presented in the article, it can be concluded that the formation of immunity to threats arising in the information space, the development of critical thinking skills, and the improvement of media literacy are important components of patriotic education. At the same time, it is necessary to form a sense of pride and responsibility in young people based on the personal example of national heroes and contemporary devotees. The proposals and recommendations presented in this article serve to further improve the national education and upbringing system, increase the social activity of youth, and thereby strengthen spiritual stability and national unity in society. Scientific analysis shows that patriotism is not just a concept, but an important spiritual foundation of national development.

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